
**DOING INDEPENDENT WORK: FOREIGN AND UZBEKISTAN
EXPERIENCE**

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Abstract. The article scientifically substantiates the experience of foreign countries and Uzbekistan in the implementation of independent work topics. It is noted that innovative development is always associated with the search for ways to solve the problems of innovative practice of teachers who introduce and develop innovative models of education. At the same time, it is justified that theoretical and methodological issues of improving the teaching of innovative activities, especially the science of labor law based on innovative educational technologies, have not been sufficiently studied.

Keywords: independent work, thinking, mental potential, opportunities, educational process, activation, increased productivity.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the issue of creating the necessary opportunities for the realization of the mental and intellectual potential of youth. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated: “In order to always stand on the world stage and in your determination to achieve your goal, you need to constantly move forward, reform your way of life and thinking. , and steadily move towards renewal” [1, 45 - p.]. Moreover, “Innovation means the future.” If we begin to build our great future today, then we must start it on the basis of innovative ideas and an innovative approach" [2, p. 19-20]. As part of the reforms being implemented today, among other things, the development of innovative thinking is being carried out, ensuring the formation of moral qualities of young people, increasing their activity in the educational process, acquiring knowledge and skills necessary for professional activities, an independent and creative approach to working on problems, and carrying out scientific research. - research work to improve mechanisms is one of the pressing problems in the system of lifelong education.

Among scientists of the Republic of Uzbekistan, innovative views related to the cluster system in teacher education are reflected in the works of Sh. Mardonov, U. Khodzhamkulov, G. Mukhamedov, Sh. Botirova. Zh. Dzhumanov, B. Prenov, S. Khudaiberdiev, U. Khudanov, B. Kholmatova, G. Yusupova, Sh. Yuldosheva studied the issues of mixed education in teaching. Also in the scientific research of A.A.

Abdukodirov, F.A. Abdukodirov, the methodology of the “Case-study” method is used in theory, practice and experience [3, 131 pp.], A.A. Abdukodirov, A.H. Paradaev - theory and methodology. technologization of the educational process, explanatory dictionary of terms related to pedagogical technology [4, 102 p.], R. Ishmukhamedov [5, 44 p.; 6, 68 pp.] – innovations and innovative technologies in education, lectures by M. Ochilov [7], O’K.Tolipov, M.Usmonboeva [8], Zh.Yoldosheva, S.Usmonov [9] theoretical and practical aspects use of pedagogical technologies in processes, Masharipova G.K. [10, 364 pp.; 11, 144 pp., 12, 210 pp., 13, 812-816 pp.] the problems of education and upbringing of youth based on the heritage of scientists are widely covered.

The problem of innovative development in the CIS has been partially studied in modern pedagogy. In particular, the prospects for the development of the T.P. system Afanasyeva, N.V. Nemova [14, 104 p.], L.N. Belotelova, V.A. Novitskaya [15, p. 41-46], history and theoretical foundations of innovative development in the field of education L.G. , 21 p.], pedagogical issues of development of additional education by T.N. Truntseva [17, 29 p.], issues of innovative development of educational institutions by V.M. Stepanov [18, 152 p.], problems of the feasibility of using innovations, evaluating innovations. , the effectiveness of G.V. Lyamin’s transformations [19, 31 b] is scientifically substantiated in scientific research.

If we analyze foreign experience, in Singapore universities independent work of students is encouraged through various mechanisms. Firstly, universities offer a wide range of self-paced courses that allow students to set their own curriculum. In addition, universities are actively using online learning platforms where students can study materials at their own pace and speed.

Secondly, students are given the opportunity to conduct independent scientific work. Publication of scientific conferences, articles and research projects is a mandatory part of the educational process. This helps students develop critical thinking and independence.

Finally, a mentoring system is common in Singapore universities, where each student is assigned a mentor who helps him develop independent skills and guides his educational activities. This approach helps to individualize learning and develop the personality of each student.

Overall, independent work arrangements at Singapore universities provide a supportive learning environment that helps students develop their skills and abilities through academic work.

In modern American universities, independent work of students occupies an important place in the educational process. In order for students to successfully implement their knowledge and skills, educational institutions use various mechanisms and methods. One of the main ways to encourage students to work

independently is to provide individual assignments and projects. This allows students to independently study the subject, assimilate the material and develop their skills. Another important mechanism is the organization of group projects, during which students learn to work in teams, exchange ideas and solve complex problems together.

Another way to develop student independence is through the use of online platforms and resources. With their help, students can use additional materials, courses and assignments, which allows them to independently study the material and test their knowledge.

Self-study mechanisms at American universities allow students to develop their skills, study independently, and apply their acquired knowledge in practice. As a result, students will be ready for professional activities.

Today, in modern British universities, independent work of students is an integral part of the educational process. To effectively implement this principle, various mechanisms are used.

Firstly, this is independent preparation for classes. Before classes, students are provided with recommended materials and literature for independent study. This approach allows students to understand the material more deeply and prepare for classroom discussion.

An important mechanism for independent work is homework. Students are asked to complete practical assignments or write an essay on a specific topic. This helps to consolidate acquired knowledge and develop independent work skills. In addition, projects and practices that students complete outside of class play an important role. This allows them to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, develop analytical thinking and communication skills.

Independent work arrangements in UK universities support students' professional development and enable them to learn independently and effectively.

In the modern educational process, special attention is paid to the development of student independence. As part of this task, Russian universities widely use various mechanisms to help develop independent work. One of the main mechanisms is the use of an individual curriculum, which allows students to independently allocate time and resources for studying subjects. This approach allows students to develop responsibility for their own learning and promotes self-discipline.

An important mechanism for encouraging independent work is the use of active learning methods such as discussions, projects and practical assignments. Such methods not only improve the assimilation of the material, but also develop students' skills in independently searching for information and solving problems. In addition, counseling and training are important mechanisms to support independent work. Teachers help students understand complex issues, guide them on the right path, and

support the motivation to independently study the material.

Russian universities widely use various mechanisms for developing students’ independent work. This contributes to their professional and personal growth, and also prepares them for independent life and work.

Contents and analysis of the results of an experimental test carried out to standardize the time spent by a student on independent tasks.

The purpose of the experimental tests is to determine the impact of the introduction of a procedure for regulating the time spent by students on determining independent educational topics and tasks on the effectiveness of the methodology for teaching subjects.

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378 students took part in the experiment. Of these, 189 students participated in experimental groups according to a program based on the standards of time spent by students on organizing independent study of science, and 189 students participated in regular groups according to a program created without taking into account the amount of time that students spend on independent study of topics and completed by them tasks.

According to the results of the experiment, students' mastery of natural subjects was 98.9 percent in experimental groups, 95.2 percent in regular groups, and quality indicators in experimental groups - 85.2 percent, in regular groups - 67.7 percent.

	Total number of students	2 (unsatisfactory)	3 (satisfactory)	4 (good)	5 (excellent)	Mastery %	Quality %
Experimental group	189	2	26	99	62	98,9	85,2
Regular group	189	9	52	80	48	95,2	67,7

The results of determining the effectiveness of the method of rationing the amount of time spent by students on independent work devoted to science are presented in order to increase the efficiency of students' mastery of independent study hours, the average level of skill and quality indicators in an experimental and educational institution. regular groups were analyzed. The results of each university and the summary result based on them were analyzed. Based on the results of the analysis, we can say that the level of development at the Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry is 1.5%, the quality indicator is 18.2%, the level of development at the Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute is 4.7%, the quality indicator is 15.6 percent, It was found that the level of development at the Namangan Textile-Industrial Institute increased by 5.1 percent, and the quality indicator increased by 18.6 percent.

This shows the effectiveness of the method of rationing the time spent by students on independent work, used in the experimental group.

Conclusion: The content of teaching “Labor Law” using innovative educational

technologies can be used in lectures or seminars, depending on the topic of the lesson. During lecture classes, you can mainly use slide presentations on the topic, mobile classes, film screenings, etc. During the seminar classes, it is recommended to use various modern pedagogical technologies and innovative methods. In this paragraph, we reviewed foreign experience in implementing independent work and the example of Uzbekistan and came to the conclusion that any independent work, distinguished by its novelty and individuality, should be implemented in practice, namely in universities. In Singapore and England, this rule is strictly observed; it is appropriate to develop and publish new materials that will contribute to the development of our economy, and not just prepare an essay or slide on a topic..

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